

THE IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF USING DIGITAL SOFTWARE TOOLS IN THE DISTANCE LEARNING SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the specifics of didactic problems when using new information technology tools in distance learning, the development and application of new information technologies and ways to overcome the negative aspects of learning.*

Keywords: *distance learning, information technology, new information technology tools.*

In organizing distance learning, it is essential to continuously communicate with learners, provide necessary methodological assistance, monitor individual tasks, and assess learners' knowledge on using modern information technologies. Now, we will focus on the didactic issues related to the application of new information technology tools in the distance learning system.

The informatization of education includes processes, methods, and a system of software and technical tools as an integral part of the process. The goal of informatization of education is to ensure the global acceleration of intellectual activity through the use of new information technologies.

The development and implementation of new information technologies is one of the ways to eliminate negative situations in education.

Let us examine the main directions: the fundamentalization of education at all levels; the formation of the education system as lifelong learning; the application of developing and innovative methods of education based on the use of modern information technologies; improving the quality of education through the development of distance learning and the use of modern information and telecommunication technologies.

Thus, one of the key factors influencing the reform of the education system is its informatization. The informatization of education, in turn, is an essential condition and an important stage of the informatization of the country. The transition from the industrial stage of societal development to the information stage is based on the use of new information technologies.

The informatization of education arises due to the use of the following important factors of new information technologies: the ability for each individual to choose their own learning path; radical changes in organizing the learning process; the creation of an effective management system for information and methodological support of education; effective organization of students' learning activities in the educational process; efficient use of the special features of computers; implementation, development, and improvement of distance learning systems at different levels.

Moreover, new information technologies provide the opportunity to solve several didactic problems: studying macro and micro-world processes and phenomena using computer graphics tools and computer modeling within complex technical and biological systems; visualizing processes at a convenient time scale for studying various physical, chemical, biological, and social processes that occur at very large or very small speeds.

New information technology tools (NIT) refer to the means that ensure the collection, processing, storage, and transmission of information, including microprocessor technology,

telecommunication systems for information exchange, and modern tools, software, hardware, and devices operating on audio-video technology.

Currently, a significant number of new information technology tools have been developed and are being used. Their number changes every year. These include: all-class computers, displays, printers, memory, audio input devices for computers, scanners, keyboards, databases, knowledge bases, multimedia systems, video text, teletext, TV information, modems, computer networks, email, electronic conferences, information retrieval systems, digital cameras, expert training systems, graphic output devices, hypertext systems, television, radio, telephones, faxes, voice email, teleconferences, electronic boards, software tools on the internet, automated libraries, educational software tools, editorial-publishing systems, CD ROMs, software packages (programming languages, translators), data transmission tools, radio stations, and others.

This list is far from exhaustive. However, it provides an idea of the various forms of new information technology tools and systems.

The pedagogical objectives of using new information technology tools include: intensifying (accelerating) all stages of the educational process; ensuring the comprehensive development of the student; preparing graduates of higher educational institutions for life in an information society; meeting social demands.

The major information and telecommunication technologies in higher education include: electronic textbooks; multimedia systems; expert systems; automatic design systems; electronic libraries; databases; local and global computing systems; email; voice email; electronic boards; teleconference systems; electronic typography.

We attempted to classify new types and tools of information technologies based on their characteristics, dividing them into 3 groups with 19 categories: A – audio, V – video, P – text, which are conditionally named.

New information technology tools (NIT) are the analogues of technical tools for teaching.
 New Information Technology Systems and Tools in the Distance Learning System.

Types of ICT Tools		New Information Technology Tools	Field of Application	Degree of Prevalence	Form of teaching
A-audio group	1.	Radio	EA	Low	Lecture
	2.	Radio Broadcasting Network	EA	Low	Lecture, Practical Lesson
	3.	Telephone	EADM	Broad	Consultation
	4.	Audiovisual	EO	Broad	Independent work
	5.	Audio Conference	EO	Periodic	Seminar
	6.	Sound Recording	EO	Periodic	Consultation
V - video group	7.	Live Sound Television Broadcast	EA	Periodic (Continuous)	Lecture, seminar

	8.	Email	EADM, EO	Low	Lecture, seminar
	9.	Slow Motion Television	EO	Low	Lecture, seminar
	10.	Television Video Tape	EO	Periodic	Lecture, seminar
	11.	Video Conference	EO	Low	Lecture, seminar
	12.	Videophone	EO	Low	Lecture, exam
	13.	Video Recording on Magnetic Media	EA	Broad	Independent work
P-Text and Graphic Group:	14.	Electronic Mail (Email)	EA	Broad	Consultation test
	15.	Computer Conferences	EA	Low	Seminar, Consultation
	16.	Fax	EADM	Broad	Consultation
	17.	Traditional Mail	EADM	Broad	Consultation test
	18.	Electronic Bulletin Board	EADM	Low	Seminar, Consultation test
	19.	TV Information (TV News)	EADM	Low	Lecture, Consultation test

(Abbreviations: EA - educational advertisement, EADM - educational administration, EO- educational objectives)

New information technologies such as teleconference and video phone tools enable the establishment of two-way communication between the teacher and students. In this process, the two-way transmission of video images, sound, and graphics is carried out simultaneously. All of this can be observed on the screens of each client's (teacher and students) monitor in three windows at the same time. During group sessions in a large auditorium, the image on the monitor can be displayed on a large screen using liquid crystal or other projection devices.

In conclusion, it can be stated that informatization of education is viewed as the practice of effectively using and creating (processing) new information technology tools, aimed at the methodology of education and the psychological-pedagogical application of teaching goals.

Additionally, informatization serves as the foundation for the development of the distance learning system.

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